

KNOWLEDGE-BASED AUTHENTICATION USING TWITTER CAN WE USE LUNCH MENUS AS PASSWORDS?

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ABSTRACT

The vast majority of online services require some form of personal authentication. Unfortunately, standard password authentication strikes a poor balance between security and convenience, whereas stronger authentication schemes, such as those involving biometrics, one-time passwords, and electronic certificates, depend on specialized hardware and/or hardware tokens. To achieve convenience, robustness, and cost-effectiveness together, we propose a scheme for dynamic knowledge-based authentication in which Twitter direct messaging is used to collect simple, memorable question/answer pairs. We also conduct a user study to evaluate the proposed scheme.

KEYWORDS

Authentication, Knowledge-based authentication, Password, Twitter

1. INTRODUCTION

The vast majority of web services use some form of password authentication, mainly due to its familiarity and ease of use. Unfortunately, the authenticating strength of a password is generally opposed to its memorability, and writing down or otherwise storing a password makes it easier to compromise. To address these deficiencies, many developers have turned to knowledge-based authentication (KBA). Broadly described, KBA [1]-[4] is a method of identifying users based on their personal knowledge. In a typical KBA scheme, a user is asked to answer one or more secret questions, as part of a multifactor authentication or self-service retrieval of a forgotten password. In this paper, we describe an innovative scheme for KBA that uses Twitter to issue questions to, and receive answers from, a given user. Specifically, the service provider asks the user a dynamic question in the form of a Twitter message, responds to the question in the form of a Twitter response message. For our target domain, we have chosen information that is commonly available, yet personalized: the user's most recent lunch menu. The effectiveness of the proposed system is demonstrated via user study and analysis.

2. WHAT IS KBA?

KBA schemes can be divided into two basic categories: static and dynamic. In static KBA, the user typically selects the questions/he would like to be asked (e.g. 'What city were you born in?', 'What colour is your car?', 'What is your favourite food?', etc.) and provides the answer(s) to these questions in advance—i.e. during registration with a given service provider (SP). The question/answer pairs are stored and used by the SP to verify the user's identity when necessary. While static KBA is relatively convenient for users, it poses distinct risks. For example, if an attacker somehow acquires the question/answer pairs for a given account, s/he can use them to impersonate the user indefinitely. For this reason, users are urged not to retain the same question/answer pair over a long period.

In a dynamic scheme, the questions asked by the SP are different each time. While this is generally safer than static KBA, it imposes an additional burden on both the SP and the user. The only way to reduce this burden is for the dynamic KBA scheme to obtain some subset of user-specific information automatically.

3. RELATED WORK

KBA has been successfully applied to a number of real services. For example, many on-line banking systems ask users to register question/answer pairs beforehand, and then pose one or all of these questions to the user when strong authentication is needed. If the user correctly answers all of the questions posed, s/he is allowed to use the service.

Figure 1 shows a typical UI for KBA. Note that in this case, the question/answer pairs are fixed around date of birth, favourite colour, and favourite animal. Although an attacker may have access to the user's date of birth, s/he is unlikely to know the answers to the other two questions. Thus, the SP will typically ask for data of birth and one of the remaining questions, reserving the third question in case the user gets an answer wrong. It is unlikely that the user will fail to answer both of the remaining questions, since they target relatively simple and memorable information.

The image shows a web form titled "Additional Security" with the instruction "Please Answer questions". It contains three input fields: "Birthday" with "month" and "day" dropdown menus, "Your Favorite color" with a "-color-" dropdown menu, and "Your Favorite animal" with a "-animal-" dropdown menu. At the bottom are "Send" and "Reset" buttons.

Figure1. A typical KBA UI

When the number of question/answer pairs is small, as in the case above, there is not much additional burden to the user. Unfortunately, the smaller the number of pairs, the easier it will be for attackers to acquire the necessary information. One can easily imagine that if Alice attends Bob’s birthday party, and manages to strike up conversations about favourite animals and colours, Bob’s bank account may soon be at risk. To mitigate this risk, we need a dynamic KBA scheme in which personalized question/answer pairs are obtained automatically.

In [5], researchers proposed a partial solution to this problem. Their system sends personal emails about which the user can be subsequently questioned. The system asks the user whether s/he has recently received e-mail from a specified sender. If s/he answers correctly, s/he is authenticated. The problem with this scheme is that it depends upon granting an e-mail server purview over personal e-mail data, and so may compromise security in other ways.

4. PROPOSED METHOD

In this paper, we propose use of Twitter [6] to store personal information for dynamic KBA. Twitter is a social networking and micro-blogging service. Users can send short, timestamped messages (of up to 140 characters) called tweets. These tweets are simpler and more user-friendly than e-mail, and can be composed and read using either a PC or mobile device. It is noteworthy that, in Japan, when the earthquake of March 2011 knocked out many other services (including many email servers), Twitter continued to function for nearly all users. As a result, the service was used to exchange information in the most stricken areas. For this reason, we consider Twitter to be a robust choice for KBA communication.

For our information domain, we have chosen to target personal lunch menus. This choice has two distinct advantages. First, almost all users in Japan consume lunch on a daily basis, irrespective of variations in breakfast and dinner plans. Second, because lunch menus tend to be simple, users generally remember the menu over the course of several days. Assuming that both the SP and user have Twitter accounts, and that each ‘follows’ the other (i.e. is subscribed to the other’s Twitter message stream), the two parties will be able to communicate directly through tweets, for the purpose of KBA. Figure 2 illustrates how this communication will proceed.

Figure 2. KBA scheme using Twitter

The steps involved in this scheme are as follows:

- 1) SP sends user Alice a direct message containing a simple question, namely 'What did you have for lunch today?'
- 2) Alice replies with a direct message containing her answer: 'Cheeseburger'. Because the question and the answer are both direct messages, other Twitter users cannot read them.
- 3) SP stores the question-answer pair, in this case: 'Lunch on February 15' - 'Cheeseburger' - 'Alice'. SP repeats step 1-3.
- 4) When Alice wants to access the SP, she sends her ID.
- 5) In return, the SP asks a question based on the information stored in Step 3: 'What did you have for lunch on February 15?' To prevent attackers from discovering and using the answer in Alice's stead, the SP sets a brief window of time during which the answer will be accepted.
- 6) Alice answers the question promptly and the SP confirms her answer. Steps 5 and 6 may be repeated several times. Alice must answer all questions correctly.
- 7) SP authenticates Alice based on her confirmed answers and grants her access to services on the SP.

Note that, in Step 5, SP can also ask questions via direct message on Twitter, in which case the SP must alert Alice accordingly: 'We have sent a question to your Twitter account. Please read this question and enter your answer here'. This strategy is more secure since it uses multiple channels of personal communication, and requires that the user also have access to her Twitter account. Figure 3 provides a sequence diagram for this strategy.

Figure 3. KBA sequence.

5. CAN WE USE A LUNCH MENU AS A PASSWORD?

The frequency and regularity of lunchtime dining make it an ideal target for dynamic authentication questions. The simple question, ‘What did you have for lunch today?’ will have an answer that tends to vary from day to day, yet remains relatively easy to remember.

Consider the simple interactions depicted in Figures 4–9. First, Alice is asked via direct message what she had for lunch today (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Tweet for a question.

She replies with a direct message (Figure 5), resulting in a parsable answer tweet (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Reply for a question on Twitter.

Figure 6. Answer tweet.

When Alice wants to accessthe SP, she logs in at the website (Figure 7).

The image shows a web service login interface. At the top, there is a grey header with the text "Web Service". Below the header, the text "Welcome to Web Service!" is displayed. The login form contains four input fields: "YourID" with the value "Alice", "Password" with masked characters "****", and "TwitterID" with the value "nemohi". There is also a "Sign In" button at the bottom of the form.

Figure 7. SP login

Finally, the SP sends the dynamic authentication question 'What did you have for lunch on January 17?' to Alice (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Authentication question tweet

Alice answers by inputting 'Cheeseburger' into the web form provided (Figure 9).

The image shows a web form for authentication. The title of the form is "Authenticates 'http://localhost/example/login.php'" and it is attributed to "by Knowledge-Based Authentication using Twitter". The main instruction is "Please enter keywords for authentication." Below this, there is an input field containing the text "Cheeseburger" and a "submit" button. At the bottom of the form, there is a section titled "To cancel the authorization." with a "Cancel" button.

Figure 9. Input answer.

If this answer is confirmed, Alice is authenticated. The question/answer process can be repeated as many times as the SP deems necessary for authentication.

6. SECURITY ANALYSIS

The multi-channel nature of our authentication strategy, coupled with Twitter's support for SSL communications, make for a highly secure system. Even if an attacker, Bob, gains regular knowledge of Alice's lunch menus, he will need to have access to her Twitter account to make any use of his knowledge. Without knowing what day the question is targeting, he will not be able to retrieve the correct answer.

7. USER STUDY

We conducted a user study often test subjects. The details of this study were as follows:

Testers: 10 university students, 21-22 years of age.

Test Period : 6 weeks: 2 weeks for collection of question/answer pairs, and 4 weeks of authenticated SP access, using the proposed strategy.

Test Method: Our server automatically sent questions via twitter direct message to all test subjects at lunch time (13:00) each day. The test subjects either ignored or answered these questions via twitter direct message. Each answer resulted in storage of a question/answer pair on the server. The users were then asked to login at the server three times per week, each time answering 3 authentication questions.

Question for KBA: Everyday

SP logins per tester: 12 (Every Tuesday, Wednesday, and Friday for the final 4 weeks)

Authentication questions at login: 3

- What was one of your lunch menus for the period beginning 3 days ago and ending yesterday?
- What was one of your lunch menus for the period beginning 7 days ago and ending four days ago?
- What was one of your lunch menus for the period beginning 14 days ago and ending 7 days ago?

Time window for each question: 10 seconds

The results of our study are given in Table 1.

The [Received] column is the rate at which a subject answered the questions sent via twitter direct message ('What did you have for lunch today?'). Note that all test subjects answered all of the sent questions. In a real-world scenario, this rate would tend to be lower than 100%.

The [Correctness] column is the rate at which a subject answered a given set of authentication questions correctly. A value of lower than 100 indicates that the given user gave at least one wrong answer.

Finally, the [Attacker] column is the rate at which an attacker answered a given set of authentication questions correctly. Attackers and their targets are chosen at random from the existing group of subjects. If the attacker answers all of the questions in a challenge set correctly, the value will be higher than 0, indicating a successful breach of security.

Note that when question scope included only the three preceding days, successful attacks did occur, and when authentication scope covered the entire two weeks, subjects found it difficult to remember the correct answer. Although the subjects can retrieve a complete record of their answers from their Twitter message feed, doing so would likely take more time than is permitted by the answer window. Our tentative conclusion is that the middle scope, one week, produces the best balance between authentication strength and the user memory span. Figure 10 shows the challenge UI that would be used in this case.

It should be noted that our attackers benefited from a worst case security scenario. Many of our subjects lunched together on a regular basis, and so had partial knowledge of one another's lunch menus. This, coupled with their prior knowledge of the attack opportunity, resulted in predictable security breaches. In a real-world scenario, gaining such advantages would require dedicated social engineering.

Table 1. Result of our KBA.

User	Received %	Correctness %			Attacker %		
		3days	1 week	2 weeks	3days	1 week	2 weeks
A	100	100	100	83	8	0	0
B	100	100	83	50	0	0	8
C	100	100	100	100	0	0	0
D	100	100	100	83	0	0	0
E	100	100	100	75	0	0	0
F	100	100	83	75	0	0	0
G	100	100	100	75	0	0	0
H	100	100	83	50	0	0	0
I	100	100	75	50	0	0	0
J	100	100	100	25	8	0	0

Knowledge-Based Authentication

Please tell me 3 menus that you ate at lunch in this week.

1:

2:

3:

Figure 10. Appropriate question.

8. FUTURE WORK

Our experiments showed a clear need to normalize answer content. If, for example, Alice produces the answer ‘hamburger’ when the correct answer was in fact ‘cheeseburger’, the system should be able to judge her answer correct within some degree of tolerance.

We might also introduce a special tag (e.g. ‘#kba’) to mark answers to implicit and/or anticipated questions. For example, if a subject uses the standard Twitter micro-blogging feature to report that ‘Today’s lunch was sushi. Delicious. #kba’, the system should be able to parse and store ‘sushi’ as today’s lunch menu, and thereby obviate the usual question/answer exchange. Since this information is public, we might then need to narrow the time window for answering (say, to 5 seconds), as an additional security measure against attentive attackers. Note that this constitutes a rather poor compromise, and could be used only in a relaxed security scenario.

9. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a knowledge-based authentication scheme that uses Twitter to obtain question/answer pairs for authentication. Although this scheme requires regular user responses to an on-going question (‘What did you have for lunch today?’), it has the potential to ease the overall security burden, for both users and service providers.

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